

PROBLEMS OF ARCHITECTURE AND CONSTRUCTION

Scientific and technical journal

e-ISSN: 2901-7845 (ISSN: 2091-5004)

2025, VOLUME-03, ISSUE-04.

The journal is included in the list of scientific journals in which scientific articles on technical sciences (construction, mechanics and machine building) and architecture are subject to publication by the decision of the OAK Board (certificate No. 00757. 2000.31.01). It is hereby notified that the articles published in English in our journal are equated to scientific articles published in foreign scientific publications in accordance with the decision of the OAK

Google Scholar provides a simple way to broadly search for scholarly literature.

Any status is accepted, from any stage of the research lifecycle.

Wikipedia is a free online encyclopedia created by volunteers around the world.

Open Journal Systems (OJS) is an open source solution to managing and publishing scholarly journals online.

MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND INNOVATIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF
UZBEKISTAN

Samarkand State Architecture and Construction University,
Samarkand, Uzbekistan.

**PROBLEMS OF ARCHITECTURE AND
CONSTRUCTION**

(Scientific and technical journal)
2025, VOLUME-03, ISSUE-04.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ АРХИТЕКТУРЫ И СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВА
(научно-технический журнал) 2025, ТОМ 3, ВЫПУСК 45383.

ME'MORCHILIK VA QURILISH MUAMMOLARI
, 2025, 3-JILD, 4-SON,

ISSN: 2091-5004, e-ISSN:2901-7845

<https://portal.issn.org/resource/ISSN/2091-5004>

Samarkand, 2025

FACTORS AFFECTING THE BUILDINGS OF THE CENTER OF PUBLIC SERVICES.

Izzat Bekturdiyev M.¹

¹teacher, Urgench State University,

Abstract: This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the main factors influencing the architectural design of public service centers. In particular, the influence of urban planning, demographic, functional-technological, climatic, and sanitary-hygienic factors on the volumetric-planning structure, functional zoning, and energy efficiency of buildings is highlighted. The study substantiates the need to create a comfortable and stable architectural environment focused on providing services to citizens and shows the advantages of atrium planning solutions in natural lighting and ventilation.

Keywords: public service center, public buildings, architectural and planning solution, urban planning factors, functional zoning, climatic and sanitary-hygienic requirements, energy saving, building with an atrium.

The main activity of the buildings of Public Service Centers is the provision of services to citizens, which is visited by a large number of citizens in one day. The architecture of the buildings of the Public Services Agency centers is formed under the mutual and joint influence of socio-economic, urban planning, climatic, sanitary-hygienic, functional, volumetric-planning, constructive, and compositional-artistic factors. For different types of buildings, depending on a number of conditions of a certain period, the influence of one or another factor becomes more significant and priority. Let's examine them sequentially.

Urban planning and territorial factors.

Urban planning factors directly affect the location, volumetric-planning structure, and appearance of the buildings of the Center for Public Services. These factors include:

- location of buildings in the city center or administrative areas;
- proximity to transport highways and public transport;
- interconnection with surrounding public buildings and open spaces;
- its role as a visual dominant or compositional element in the urban environment.

In regional centers, Public Service Centers are often formed as an important element of the city's administrative and social core.

Demographic and social factors. The size, density, and social composition of the population influence the capacity and functional structure of buildings. Specifically:

- large population in regional centers requires an increase in the volume of services;
- the age structure of the population (elderly, young families, families with children) creates the need to organize special rooms in buildings;
- the diversity of citizens' needs for public services requires the diversification of types of services.

These factors are the main criteria for determining the composition and functional zoning of premises.

Functional and technological factors.

The effectiveness of the service process in public service centers is closely related to the internal functional structure of buildings. Functional and technological factors include:

- separation of citizen and employee flows;
- organization of the queue system;
- logical interconnection of service rooms;
- creation of infrastructure for digital services.

These factors require the formation of architectural and planning solutions based on the "user-oriented" principle.

Socio-economic factors. Buildings and complexes intended for institutions and enterprises serving society and the population belong to the public. The service sector is an important component of the national economic complex. The role of service industries in social production is enormous and diverse. They provide leadership in social systems; constitute an important phase of economic production - exchange, linking social production and personal consumption; allow for the reproduction of labor power; influence the nature of personal consumption and the household structure.

Climatic factors. It is known that in the construction of buildings on the territory of our republic, the following construction zones are distinguished from each other.

I Regions under the active influence of desert climate include regions located in the lowlands of our republic.

Zone II includes oases and valleys located at the foot of the mountains.

The III zone includes mountainous regions. The climate of the regions of the I zone is characterized by consistently hot dry winds: garmsel, dust storms, and high external air temperatures. Such a dry climate is characteristic of the southeastern parts of the Karakum Desert: the Bukhara-Surkhandarya oasis and the developed regions of the Karshi and Mirzachul massifs.

II. The foothill regions of the zone are subject to the influence of deserts in small quantities and have favorable climatic conditions with favorable landscapes. These zones include the foothills of the Tashkent, Jizzakh, and Samarkand regions of the Fergana region, and some districts of the Kashkadarya oasis.

III. The zone includes high-mountain areas (located at an altitude of 2000 m above sea level). The weather in these regions differs sharply from each other. When building

public service centers, we must take these climate-vulnerable regions into account.

Sanitary and hygienic factors. It is one of the most important and structural factors in the formation of architectural and planning solutions for the buildings of the Center for Public Services. Since these buildings are characterized by continuous and mass visits by citizens, the creation of a healthy indoor environment, ensuring natural lighting and ventilation, as well as energy-saving planning are of paramount importance.

Sanitary and hygienic requirements are manifested in the following main aspects:

- taking into account the climatic conditions of the territory when determining the orientation and configuration of buildings;
- ensuring adequate natural lighting of service rooms, workplaces, and waiting areas;
- natural ventilation and air exchange of premises;
- energy-efficient planning of heating and cooling systems in accordance with climatic conditions;
- use of green elements to create a comfortable microclimate in the building;
- application of energy-intensive buildings, formed on the basis of the principles of dynamic adaptation.

Sanitary and hygienic aspects of organizing natural lighting. Natural lighting in public service centers directly affects the psychological state of citizens, the effectiveness of service provision, and the working conditions of employees. It is especially important to ensure the level of natural lighting for service halls, reception rooms, and workplaces.

In the buildings of the Center for Public Services, where atrium planning solutions are used, the issue of natural lighting is of particular importance. The methods for calculating illumination, developed for traditional corridor layout schemes, are not fully suitable for buildings with an atrium, since in such buildings, sunlight propagates by reflecting several times before reaching the work premises. Therefore, atrium spaces are considered as an additional natural light source for service rooms.

To ensure the required level of natural lighting in rooms located around the atrium, it is advisable to reduce the width of the rooms or increase the floor height. Practice shows that at a standard floor height, it is possible to achieve satisfactory natural lighting in rooms no wider than 12 meters. It is possible to further improve these indicators by increasing

the height of the floor and using special elements reflecting lighting.

Natural ventilation and microclimate formation. Maintaining normal air circulation and microclimate in public service center buildings due to large population flows is considered sanitary and hygienically important. Atrium planning solutions create additional opportunities in this regard. The atrium serves as an air reservoir and a natural ventilation duct, creating a natural draft force in the building due to the upward movement of hot air.

This process allows for the natural removal of air from buildings and the attraction of external air. As a result, the need for mechanical ventilation is partially reduced, and sanitary, hygienic, and energy efficiency indicators are improved.

Energy saving and environmental efficiency. Sanitary and hygienic factors are closely related to the energy efficiency of Public Service Center buildings. The "greenhouse effect" arising from the use of solar radiation in atrium buildings is a positive factor in heating buildings in winter and creating an additional load on cooling in summer. Therefore, atrium solutions can be designed based on two different functional scenarios: heating or cooling.

In addition, through integrated control of natural and artificial lighting sources, it is possible to optimize the consumption of lighting energy during the day. In cases of insufficient natural lighting, the phased commissioning of artificial lighting systems contributes to energy saving.

CONCLUSION

The research results show that the buildings of public service centers are complex public structures aimed at providing mass and uninterrupted services to the population. Their architectural formation is carried out on the basis of the harmonious and complex interaction of socio-economic, urban

planning, demographic, climatic, sanitary-hygienic, and functional-technological factors. Each of these factors plays an important role in the volumetric-planning structure, functional zoning, and compositional solutions of the building.

Urban planning and territorial factors determine the place of public service centers in the urban environment and ensure their integration with transport and public spaces. Demographic and social factors determine the capacity of buildings, types of services and the composition of premises, and require the creation of an environment adapted to the various needs of users. Functional and technological factors serve to increase the efficiency of the service process and indicate the need to form "user-oriented" architectural solutions.

Consideration of climatic and sanitary-hygienic factors makes it possible to ensure a healthy indoor environment, a favorable microclimate, and energy savings in buildings. In particular, atrium planning solutions play an important role in reducing operating costs and increasing environmental efficiency by improving natural lighting and ventilation.

In general, when designing the buildings of public service centers, it is important to harmonize regional conditions, the needs of the population, and modern technologies. This approach serves to create a comfortable, effective, and sustainable architectural environment for citizens, as well as to improve the quality of public services.

REFERENCES

1. Ministry of Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2019). KMK 2.08.02-19. Public buildings and structures. Tashkent. (Volume-planning, sanitary-hygienic, and functional requirements for public buildings)
2. Ministry of Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2017). KMK 2.01.01-17. Construction Climatology. Tashkent. (I, II, III

climatic zones, influence of climatic factors on building architecture)

3. Ministry of Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2020). SHNK 2.01.05-20. Natural and artificial lighting. Tashkent. (Natural lighting, lighting standards in buildings with an atrium)

4. Ministry of Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2020). SHNK 2.04.05-20. Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning. Tashkent. (Natural ventilation, microclimate, and air exchange)

